

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

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Language use and linguistic variation in multilingual groups of speakers in Ngaoundéré (North Cameroon) (II)

Sprachgebrauch und linguistische Variation in multilingualen Sprechergruppen in Ngaoundéré (Nord-Kamerun) (II)

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2 Summary

In its second phase, the project focused on the local language Mbum (Adamawa, Kebi-Benue), which had already been identified in the first phase as being strongly influenced by interference phenomena. The multilingual ecology of the Adamawa Plateau and in particular of the provincial capital Ngaoundéré produces language variations that are expressed in different ways in different social groups and show different usage patterns.

Multilingual contexts such as those found on the Adamawa Plateau continue to pose a challenge for contact linguistics, as they are characterized by low normative forces, little or no linguistic codification and a high degree of dynamism and fluidity. Such contexts, which are the norm rather than the exception worldwide, still play a rather marginal role in linguistic theory building with regard to language change, emergence and social functions. This circumstance has led to models that are characterized by a Global North bias and ignore many important aspects of language change and norm maintenance.

The project set out to reducing this bias by collecting and analysing empirical data on linguistic variations in the local language Mbum and ultimately making them available to the public in appropriate database formats. The modelling based on the empirical data initially aims to understand how linguistic variation spreads, is maintained and contributes to language change. Particular attention was paid to multilingual speakers and their everyday language mix by recording and analysing communication in different contexts. For extreme cases in which a distinction between the various elements in terms of individual languages makes no sense or is just not possible, a new, language-independent but speaker group-specific type of representation is also being developed.

Zusammenfassung

Das Projekt nahm in seiner zweiten Phase die Sprache Mbum (Adamawa, Kebi-Benue) in den Blick, die bereits in der ersten Phase als sehr stark von Interferenzerscheinungen geprägt erkannt wurde. Die multilinguale Ökologie des Adamawa-Plateaus und insbesondere der Provinzhauptstadt Ngaoundéré bringt dabei Sprachvariationen hervor, die in unterschiedlichen sozialen Gruppen auf verschiedene Weise ausgeprägt sind und unterschiedliche Gebrauchsmuster zeigen.

Multilinguale Kontexte, wie sie auf dem Adamawa-Plateau anzutreffen sind, stellen nach wie vor eine Herausforderung für die Kontakt-Linguistik dar, da sie geprägt sind durch geringe normierende Kräfte, keine oder geringe sprachliche Kodifizierung und ein Höchstmaß an Dynamik und Fluidität. Solche Kontexte, die weltweit eher die Norm als die Ausnahme bilden,

spielen in der linguistischen Theoriebildung hinsichtlich Sprachwandel, -entstehung und sozialen Funktionen noch immer eine eher marginale Rolle. Dieser Umstand führte zu Modellen, die durch einen Global-North-Bias gekennzeichnet sind und viele wichtigen Aspekte von Sprachwandel und Normerhalt außen vorlassen.

Das Projekt trat an, einen Beitrag zur Verringerung dieses Bias zu leisten, indem es empirische Daten zu linguistischen Variationen der lokalen Sprache Mbum sammelt, analysiert und schließlich in entsprechenden Datenbankformaten der Öffentlichkeit zur Verfügung stellt. Die Modellbildung anhand der empirischen Daten zielt zunächst darauf ab zu verstehen, wie sich sprachliche Variation verbreitet, erhält und zum Sprachwandel beiträgt. Dabei wurde insbesondere auf multilinguale Sprecher und deren alltäglichen Sprachenmix eingegangen, indem Kommunikation in verschiedenen Kontexten aufgenommen und analysiert wurde. Für extremen Fälle, in denen eine einzelsprachliche Unterscheidung der verschiedenen Elemente nicht möglich oder sinnvoll ist, wird zudem eine neue, sprachenunabhängige aber sprechergruppenspezifische Art der Darstellung entwickelt.

3 Progress Report

3.1 Original questions and goals

Based on results from the first phase (cp. project report in the renewal proposal from 14.02.2020), I focused on three interrelated goals in the second phase.

Firstly, I intended to study propagation of linguistic variation in small local networks. More specifically, I aimed at documenting loosely connected (or marginal) actors from the Mbum speaking urban community and their communication with more central and better connected actors from their personal networks. The idea was to check the hypothesis that marginal actors, i.e. actors who have fewer and less frequent connections within their personal networks, feed linguistic innovations into more stable groups of actors, i.e. actors who are bound by more frequent and multiple ties (Beyer 2017:14, 15), from where these innovations then start to develop normative power through frequency rise and usage by more central actors and norm builders. In terms of network relations, we learned in the first project phase that the Ngaoundéré motorcycle taxi drivers represent this type of marginal actors and consequently intended to continue with actors from this group.

The second goal was closely connected to the first one in documenting the ubiquitous variation in the urban form of Mbum. To that end, the proposition was to collect linguistic material of contemporary urban Mbum and compare it to less 'urbanized' country varieties. The intention

was to build a database of contemporary Mbum that helps to assess the frequency and importance of contact induced variation therein. Some of the questions were: Is it mainly on the phonetic/phonological and lexical tier where contact-induced variation is apparent or are other layers of the urban lects likewise affected? Are there specific grammatical systems that are more prone to contact induced interference than others?

The third mission of the project was, again, closely related to the first two goals and intended a grammatical description accounting for the fact that different groups of Mbum speakers use different forms of the language including different levels of contact-induced interferences. Given the epistemological dilemma apparent in traditional description of language contact outcomes, namely relying on monolingual grammars on one hand while realizing that it is often not possible to assign a given grammatical element to either of the languages involved, the idea was to apply a more adaptive way in the description of contact outcome. To that end, I proposed to apply the concept of Diasystematic Construction Grammar (DCxG) (Boas & Höder 2018) and see how it works with the Mbum data at hand.

3.2 Empirical data, field research

The original idea of gathering empirical data during a series of fieldtrips of two researchers had to be revised. For one, the proposed doctoral position was not granted so that I had to readjust the planning according to available man power. Secondly, and unfortunately more important, I personally faced increasing health problems that forced me to reduce my field research time in Cameroon substantially. My only field trip in October 2022 which was, despite its short time span of only 20 days, quite fruitful in terms of data for the first goal (cp. above). I also convinced the originally proposed PhD candidate, Janika Kunzmann, to continue work on her planned dissertation of a grammatical description of Mbum and to work for the project either as student helper or on a freelance contract basis. In these capacities, she undertook three field trips to Cameroon (October 2022 (together with me), March/April 2023, October 2024) and thus added substantial material to the Mbum lexical database and the morpho-syntactic description of contemporary Mbum. On her second trip, Sören Zimmermann, a doctor of law and bachelor student in Empirical linguistics with a focus on African languages, accompanied her and conducted interviews on the topic of his BA-thesis, namely traditional land- and inheritance laws. Alongside this, he was charged to support Kunzmann in her field research by generating discussions on various subjects and with different groups of Mbum speakers. As he was new to the field and not acquainted with the moto taxi drivers, he couldn't continue my work on innovation propagation through the MTD networks.

3.3 Results and outcomes

3.3.1 Propagation of innovation

Although I only conducted empirical research during the short field trip in October 2022, some interesting insights have been reached in describing processes of innovation propagation and language use in specific contexts. As I lay out in a recent paper (cp. Beyer 2024) there are hints to a very pragmatic use of variation by the speakers.

For instance, I observed the use of the notion for ‘dog’ in a conversation between two friends (M1 and M2) and a customer. As I knew from earlier recordings (Beyer 2022) the usual word for ‘dog’ of my informant (M1, a motor taxi driver) was the regular Mbum word *góy*, pl. *góy-rì*. During a conversation with M2 (a motor mechanic working in a roadside garage), he switches to the Ngaoundéré-Fulfulde version *góy-rù*, pl. *góy-ji*, conflating the Mbum lexeme with the appropriate Fulfulde noun class markers. At one point, M1 briefly switches to the standard Fulfulde term *boosaa-ru* but immediately corrects himself, signaling his awareness that this form is not appropriate in their shared communicative context. When a customer, a speaker of a different Mbum dialect (Mbum-Pana), joins the conversation, M2 uses the Mbum-Pana word *váa* for ‘dog’. Both M1 and M2 then continue using *váa* alongside the Fulfulde-influenced *góy-rù*, adjusting their language choices to include the customer's dialect (Beyer 2024: 8,9). This example shows how speakers adapt their multilingual repertoire to the context at hand. In this center-of-town street-side context, the two friends use the standard Ngaoundéré vehicular despite them sharing the same L1, Mbum. They both also comfort the customer by occasionally using his vernacular term that both other participants are familiar with. Whether and how such encounters really have effects on any standard forms of the languages involved is however uncertain. Unfortunately, I hadn't the chance to investigate this line of research any further.

Numerous examples of variation in Mbum show the huge bandwidth of possibilities concerning the mix between Mbum and Fulfulde without always being defined as such by the speakers themselves. For instance, Ngaoundéré based young speakers use two differently lexicalized versions of a presentative construction (Beyer 2024:9,10) seemingly without even being aware of the differences. In an interview I was conducting with one of the speakers online in 2023, he said that no one of his peers would bother about the ‘Mbum or Fulfulde?’ question, but during the occasional visits of his paternal family on the countryside he would probably be corrected when using the more Fulfulde like version. Anyway, out of respect for his elders he would try to avoid speaking to much of what he called during this interview ‘Ngaoundéré Mbum’.

Another telling example was recorded by Kunzmann during the second field research in spring 2023. She had a field assistant reflecting on versions of sentences that he might use with his peers. The guy came up with four versions of a sentence that range from an allegedly ‘pure’

up-country Mbum to a clear Ngaoundéré-Fulfulde construction and claimed that all of those are part of his and his peers' repertoires (Beyer 2024:10,11). He also reckoned, he and his peers would probably use a mixed version among themselves reserving the other two for appropriate situations like speaking with Mbum elders or conversing with unknown people in the city of Ngaoundéré. One interesting element in this recording is the reinterpretation of the Fulfulde 1pl.exclusive pronoun *min* that the speaker (and his peers) use as 1sg.emphatic pronoun *mìn* in their version of Mbum. As Kunzmann (04.11.2023) states, this is not a familiar use in any other Mbum version we have encountered so far. So it stands to see, whether and how this element takes on in other Mbum versions and if it might reach the point of generalized standard use?

There are many more examples in the data that are still in the process of being analysed. All of them seem to indicate that a rigorous dividing line between versions, varieties and even languages is sometimes hard to draw. This is even more so the case when it is language use in specific groups who are apparently developing specific codes reflecting their specific repertoires.

3.3.2 Documentation of variation, database

Data elicitation and analysis was mainly in the hands of the project collaborator Janika Kunzmann. Based on her long term acquaintance with the project as a student helper, she decided to do her PhD in form of a comprehensive grammatical description of Mbum as spoken in the rural village Nganha, in the wider vicinity of Ngaoundéré. In her research on the rural Mbum variant of Nganha, she paid close attention to linguistic variation and the parameters involved in the linguistic choices of the speakers she worked with. Janika Kunzmann continued to build up the lexical database on Mbum using the software tool FieldWorks Language Explorer (FLEX) which already started in the first project phase. This database now serves as a structured repository of lexical data and related meta data for Mbum, facilitating both, linguistic analysis and documentation (cp. 3.4 below).

Most importantly, the database also contains different variants of lexemes and notes on their use (e.g., used by younger vs older generations, used in rural vs urban contexts, etc.). To give an example, the database can be searched for lexical items that translate to the English gloss "all". The database then shows three entries: *wàpát*, *wàmbáp* and *wàkáp*. A look into the lexical entries will show that the quantifiers differ in their semantics, but also that their use is distributed based on speakers age: whereas older generations in Nganha use *wàmbáp* and *wàkáp*, the former referring to humans, the latter referring to animals and objects, younger speakers

in Nganha use *wàpát* to refer to humans and animals as well as objects (Kunzmann, forthcoming). Each lexical item can be traced back to the speaker who uttered it in the elicitation process, and information about the speaker collected in short linguistic-biographical interviews. All personal data is anonymized.

Currently, work on the database is still ongoing. It is uploaded in a data repository (cp. 3.4 below) to be accessible for third parties. Kunzmann actively uses the database for work on her doctoral thesis, e.g. by filtering the lexical database for “minimal pairs” serving as a proof of distinct phonemes in the phonology section of her dissertation. She also up-dates the database in the repository constantly as the analysis evolves.

A further outcome of our neat documentation of phonological variation by different speakers led the team to delve deeper into the documentation history of Mbum. It was specifically the pronunciation of labial-velar consonants that took our attention as they seemed very unstable and versatile. A closer look at contemporary and old sources (some of them more than a hundred years old) underpinned the unstable nature of this phoneme and led us to a two sided conclusion: On the one hand, there are strong hints that labial-velars can be reconstructed for the proto phoneme system of the Kébi-Bénue family of which Mbum is a part. On the other hand, there are also strong indications that this phoneme is prone to socially induced manipulation in form of identity building and signalling of group solidarity (Beyer & Kunzmann 2022).

3.3.3 A Diasystematic Constuction Grammar of Mbum speakers

The title of this section reveals a key point of the enterprise, namely to account for a grammar not as a property of a language but as a property of the speakers who use it. As unfamiliar and strange as this may sound in the first place, there are good arguments for looking upon language use by multilinguals in an environment like Ngaoundéré in such a way. As Höder (2014, 2018) puts it, speakers in bi- or multilingual groups create a common system for all their languages. Therefore, the (speech)community is to be conceived as the primary carrier of grammar, not the single language.

Following up on these theoretical claims, the idea was to gather empirical data from such contexts where speakers apparently use their multilingual repertoires in a community specific way. As outlined in two recent publications (Beyer 2024: 8,9; Beyer 2025: 318) one could render the discourse data of a local group of friends (as described in 3.3.1, second paragraph) as a cross-language construction network. Taking the example of the lexical construction denoting the notion ‘dog’, the diaconstruction (cp. Figure 1) depicts multiple lexical forms from different lan-

guages and varieties that coexist in the construction network. The speakers now select a phonological forms based on the communicative context and the goals they want to achieve rather than adhering to strict language boundaries:

Figure 1: Lexical diaconstruction 'dog' as part of the grammar used by young speakers in Ngaoundéré with a linguistic background in Mbum

In this case the brackets show four different sources for the phonological filling:

- C(NgMb) represents the 'normal' word for 'dog' which is commonly used in any version of contemporary Mbum, be it a more traditional up-country variety or what is called Ngaoundéré Mbum by the local speakers. Its pragmatic use is restricted to situations where all discourse participants know for sure that they all have the same linguistic Mbum-background.
- C(NgF) i.e. Ngaoundéré Fulfulde, the localized version of standard Fulfulde spoken all over northern Cameroon. This phonological form is used to highlight the local Ngaoundéré context but not necessarily with all participants from a Mbum background. It is pragmatically quite neutral and would be the first choice whenever a group-outsider is present.
- C(GaF) this Garoua Fulfulde (representing the standard form of Fulfulde in Northern Cameroon) filling of the diaconstruction was only used once in the above described context (cp. 3.3.1). Although we have no empirical data that confirm this element being part of the diaconstruction network (as the speaker who used it corrected himself immediately) we assume so, as it stems from the lingua franca of Northern Cameroon and as such it is highly likely a part of the group's shared common repertoire. It was only in the context at the road-side garage that it seemed to be inappropriate to the speaker.

- C(Mb-P) depicts the original word in the Mbum-Pana variety. As it comes out in the conversation, both members of the friends group are familiar with it and are willing to accommodate the customer by using it interchangeably with the C(NgF) version.

More examples of diaconstructions can be found in Beyer (2024, 2025). Their combination in a (dia)construction network reflects how multilingual speakers organize their entire linguistic repertoire as a single, shared system rather than with separate language modules. A more comprehensive representation of the diaconstruction network of the specific group of Ngaoundéré based friends from the motorcycle taxi driver and mechanics sphere is currently in preparation.

3.4 Research data, quality management

The empirical data will be accessible in two formats:

The lexical data base is in FLEEx format. The current set-up was mainly developed by the project collaborator Janika Kunzmann. She also keeps entertaining the database and constantly adds new data as they come in from ongoing analyses. The database can be used for morphological parsing and interlinear glossing of Mbum texts, as well as for semantic categorization, filtering and other features related to lexical data, making it an ideal platform for the analysis of the linguistic data. It includes not only the documentation of about 950 lexical items but also integrates phonetic, phonological, morphological, and semantic information, ensuring that the database is both, comprehensive and accessible for future research. The lexemes are given in their phonological form, but also in phonetic transcription if it diverges from the phonological one. Each lexeme is translated into French, the language in which the data was elicited, and English, and is linked with information on its syllable structure, tone and word class. Where applicable, the lexical entries carry notes on their etymology, phonology and semantics.

The second format is based on the ELAN software and contains transcripts of group communications, mainly from the young urban Mbum speakers in the city of Ngaoundéré. The data are interlinearized and annotated and connected to the respective sound files. As this work is very demanding and time consuming, there are – for the time being – only a few files ready for upload. However, as the analysis of the data continues, this dataset will also grow and gain importance. The sound files will be publicly available after Kunzmann has finished her doctoral thesis, as they are the main basis for her ongoing analysis.

Meta data of the speakers and the circumstances of the recordings are also neatly documented and part of both data sets. There are sound files available for every entry so that the segmental and suprasegmental transcriptions can be verified. A first version of the lexical database in

FLEx (Kunzmann 2025) as well as a view ELAN files and texts are already accessible in the Zenodo repository.

3.5 References (only those are listed that don't figure under 4.1)

- Beyer, Klaus. 2017. Language development under multilingual conditions: towards an agent based simulation of contact-induced language development. In Beyer, Klaus and Raija Kramer (eds.), *Language contact and change under multilingual conditions. Case studies from Africa*. Frankfurter Afrikanistische Blätter (FAB) 24 - 2012. Cologne: Rüdiger Köppe Verlag, pp. 11-27.
- Boas, H. C. and S. Höder. 2018. Construction Grammar and language contact. An introduction. In Boas, H.C. and S. Höder (eds.), *Constructions in contact: Constructional perspectives on contact phenomena in Germanic languages*. Amsterdam, Philadelphia: Benjamins, pp. 5-36.
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4 Published Project Results

4.1 Publications with scientific quality assurance

- Beyer, Klaus. 2022. Motorcycle taxi drivers in Ngaoundéré, Cameroon: Communication in a diffuse multilingual setting. In Smakman, Dick, Jiří Nekvapil and Kapitolina Fedorova (eds.), *Postmodern Individuals in Urban Communicative Settings. Studies in Language and Identity*. New York: Routledge, pp. 49-63.
- Beyer, Klaus. 2024. A diasystematic approach to multilingual ecology: The case of Mbum speakers in Ngaoundéré, Cameroon. In Yang, Mimi (ed.), *Multilingualism in its multiple dimensions*. London: IntechOpen, p. 11-26. doi:10.5772/intechopen.1005055.
- Beyer, Klaus. 2025. Code-Switching Practices in West Africa. In Darquennes, Jeroen, Joseph C. Salmons and Wim Vandenbussche (eds.), *Language contact: An international hand-*

book. (Handbücher zur Sprach- und Kommunikationswissenschaft / Handbooks of Linguistics and Communication Science, HSK 45.2). Berlin & Boston: De Gruyter, pp. 307-321.

Beyer, Klaus & Janika Kunzmann. 2022. Retracing labial-velar consonants in Mbum (Adamawa): Between genetic transmission and language contact. *Afrika und Übersee* 95, pp. 25-48. <https://doi.org/10.15460/auue.2022.95.1.270>.

Kunzmann, Janika. 2025. Lexical data of Mbum language (Adamawa, Cameroon) in FLEx format [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15020329>

Kunzmann, Janika (accepted): Contact-induced change on the Adamawa Plateau: Mbum in contact with Fulfulde. In: Shinagawa, Daisuke (ed.) (forthcoming), *Describing linguistic dynamics in Africa* [interim]. Tokyo: Research Institute for Languages and Cultures of Asia and Africa.

4.2 Other publications and published results

Beyer, Klaus. 2020. Annual report of the project. In *ZIAF – Zentrum für interdisziplinäre Afrikaforschung*, Goethe-Universität, Frankfurt, p. 40, 41.

Beyer, Klaus. 2021. Annual report of the project. In *ZIAF – Zentrum für interdisziplinäre Afrikaforschung*, Goethe-Universität, Frankfurt, p. 45.

Beyer, Klaus. 2022. Annual report of the project. In *ZIAF – Zentrum für interdisziplinäre Afrikaforschung*, Goethe-Universität, Frankfurt, p. 41.

Beyer, Klaus. 2024. Annual report of the project. In *ZIAF – Zentrum für interdisziplinäre Afrikaforschung*, Goethe-Universität, Frankfurt, p. 37.

Zimmermann, Sören. 2023. “Mbok Mbum yàŋ yàŋà-yàŋá yàŋ. Reduplication in Mbum. Findings of recent fieldwork in Northern Cameroon”. Seminar paper handed-in at the Department of Linguistics, Goethe University Frankfurt.

Zimmermann, Sören. 2023. “Interrogative particles in Mbum”. Seminar paper handed-in at the Department of Linguistics, Goethe University Frankfurt.

Talks

Beyer, Klaus. 25.08.2018. “The engine room of language change. Motorcycle taxi drivers in Ngaoundéré, Northern Cameroon”. Conference paper presented at WOCAL 9, Rabat, Morocco.

- Beyer, Klaus. 25.06.2019. "Social Network Challenges. Sociolinguistic analysis of multilingual speaker interaction in Ngaoundéré (Cameroon)". Paper presented at the Linguistic Colloquium of IAAW at Humboldt-University.
- Beyer, Klaus. 01.07.2021. "Motorcycle taxi drivers in Ngaoundéré, Cameroon: Marginal actors as source of linguistic innovation?". Paper presented at the 24. Afrikanistentag, Frankfurt am Main.
- Kunzmann, Janika. 31.08.2022. "Mbum (Adamawa) nouns and verbs: Tone patterns and (puzzling) alternations". Presentation held at the 51st Colloquium of African Languages and Linguistics (CALL) at Leiden University in Leiden, Netherlands.
- Kunzmann, Janika. 09.11.2022. "Preliminary findings on the phonology of Mbum (Adamawa)". Presentation held at the Llacan colloquium at Institut national des langues et civilisations orientales in Paris, France.
- Kunzmann, Janika. 07.12.2022. "Describing an understudied language of Northern Cameroon: Prominent phonetic and phonological features of Mbum (Adamawa)". Presentation held at the Phonology Colloquium at Goethe University in Frankfurt am Main, Germany.
- Kunzmann, Janika. 05.05.2023. "Nominal composition and derivation in Mbum (Adamawa)". Presentation held at the Afrikanist*innentag at Leipzig University in Leipzig, Germany.
- Kunzmann, Janika & Sören Zimmermann. 13.09.2023. "Form and function of reduplication in Mbum (Nghanha and Ngaoundéré)". Presentation held at the 2nd Adamawa Conference at the Institut national des langues et civilisations orientales in Paris, France.
- Kunzmann, Janika. 04.11.2023. "What is Mbum and what is not? Addressing multi- and translingualism in the creation of a reference grammar". Presentation held at the "A new perspective on descriptive linguistics in Africa based on the translingual ecology" international workshop at Tokyo University of Foreign Studies, Japan.
- Kunzmann, Janika. 06.11.2023. "Mbum (Adamawa, Cameroon) in areal contact: Salient segmental phonological features". Presentation held at the 1st Osaka Contact Linguistics Colloquium at Osaka University, Japan.
- Kunzmann, Janika. 07.08.2024. "A system between tone and stress? The assignment of tone in Mbum (Adamawa) nominal plural constructions". Presentation held at the 11th World Congress of African Linguistics at University of Nairobi, Kenya.